

A Proposal for an experiment to measure the velocity of the reference frame with respect to velocity of light, and preliminary experiment results

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Abstract— A practical experimental setup to measure the velocity of the reference frame with respect to the velocity of the light is discussed. The mathematical derivation is shown. Proof of concept setup is explained. The implications of measuring the velocity of the local reference frame with respect to the velocity of light is discussed.

I. INTRODUCTION

Starting with the famous Michelson Morley experiment, many attempts have been made to measure the velocity of the reference frame with respect to the velocity of the light. Though originally, Michelson and Morley tried to measure the velocity of the earth against “luminiferous ether”, that failed experiment spawned Lorentz transformations and special relativity theory, which has been found very successful in every measurement. Special theory of relativity authored by Albert Einstein has proved to be one of the most successful theories, though it has the postulate that the “light is always propagated in empty space with a definite velocity c which is independent of the state of motion of the emitting body”.

But this does not preclude the possibility that the velocity of the reference frame can be measured against the velocity of the light. But in the principle of relativity, another postulate of Einstein says that “the states of the physical systems are not affected, whether these changes of state be referred to the one or the other of two systems in uniform translatory motion relative to each other”.

Finding different velocities of light in different frames of reference will disprove the postulate that the reference frames are indistinguishable.

The experimental setup explained in this paper shows a way in which such a measurement of the velocity of the local reference frame can be measured against the velocity of the light. The mathematics proves that it can be done too.

II. TWO POSTULATES OF SPECIAL THEORY OF RELATIVITY

A. *The general laws of nature are to be expressed by equations which hold good for all systems of co-ordinates, that is, are co-variant with respect to any substitutions whatever (generally co-variant).(1)*

If the velocity of the reference frame be measurable in any frame of reference, this would indicate the velocity of light is different in different frames of references. Thus, proving this postulate is not consistent with the nature.

B. *As measured in any inertial frame of reference, light is always propagated in empty space with a definite velocity c that is independent of the state of motion of the emitting body.*

While the velocity of light be independent of the motion of the emitting body, this does not preclude the possibility that the velocity of the local reference frame be measured.

III. MATH

Let us consider Young’s double slit experiment. This experiment proved the wave nature of the light. This age-old experiment can prove the velocity of light is different in different directions as well.

The negative result of Michelson-Morley experiment is explained by R.P. Feynmann et al (2) as the time taken on both light paths remains the same, either in longitudinal vs the transverse arms of the apparatus.

If the velocity of local reference frame is u , and the light travels in that direction, velocity of light relative to the apparatus is $c - u$, so the time is the length L divided by $c - u$

On the longitudinal the time taken is

$$T_l = \frac{L}{c - u} + \frac{L}{c + u}$$

And due to length contraction, this becomes

$$T_l = \frac{2L}{\sqrt{c^2 - u^2}}$$

On the transverse the time taken is

$$T_t = \frac{2L}{\sqrt{c^2 - u^2}}$$

Both the times being the same, we don't observe the phase difference. This explanation assumes the light travels $c - u$ in one direction, where u is the velocity of the local reference frame of the interferometer and $c + u$ in opposite direction.

Young's experiment on double slit provides an alternate way to look at the velocity of the local reference frame with respect to the velocity of light.

The below figure details how the path length difference for waves travelling from two different slits create interference patterns on the screen.

The lengths S1 to k and S3 to k are of the same length. The distance S2 to S3, that is Δl , is the additional length the light from the slit S2 needs to take to travel.

The phase difference between the two rays of light can be calculated as

$$\psi = \frac{d \sin \theta}{\lambda} 2\pi$$

- Eq 3.1

Figure 1: Phase difference in the Young's double slit experiment when the light that goes from S2 to k travels at the opposite direction the local reference frame is moving at velocity u in direction as indicated.

As we can rewrite $\lambda = c/f$

$$\psi = \frac{f d \sin \theta}{c} 2\pi$$

- Eq 3.2

If the local reference frame travels at the direction as the line S2 to k, then the velocity of the light would be $c+u$ in the direction of the reference frame.

Plugging this in the above equation

$$\psi = \frac{f d \sin \theta}{c + u} 2\pi$$

- Eq 3.3

If we rotate the above double slit experiment setup 180 degrees, the velocity of light would be $c-u$

$$\psi = \frac{f d \sin \theta}{c - u} 2\pi$$

- Eq 3.4

Since the Lorentz length contraction reduces the length along the line of velocity of the reference frame, we need to include the γ factor to modify the length of the path difference where

$$\gamma = \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{u^2}{c^2}}}$$

so the equation becomes

$$\psi = \frac{f d \sin \theta}{\gamma(c + u)} 2\pi$$

- Eq 3.5

And at 180-degree rotation of the setup, the phase difference becomes

$$\psi = \frac{f d \sin \theta}{\gamma(c - u)} 2\pi$$

- Eq 3.6

IV. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

The following setup was done to prove the proof of concept of the above equations, rather than to find the exact velocity of the earth's reference frame.

A double slit experiment is constructed on a rotating table as depicted below.

Figure 2: Experimental setup to identify the phase difference in opposite directions.

The screen and a camera is setup on a table extending from the rotating table. A laser pointer is placed on the rotating table pointing to the double slit close to it. This laser light creates the double slit interference pattern in the screen. But the central interference pattern is angled at a specific angle

Calculating for the following numbers

$$d = 1 \text{ mm}$$

$$\theta = 10 \text{ degrees}$$

$$\text{And suppose } u = 300000 \text{ m/s}$$

For $\lambda = 550 \text{ nm}$, we can calculate the frequency as

$$f = 545077196363636.00 \text{ per second}$$

If we plugin the values, we get

On the c+u direction we get 315.40 phase difference

This means 315 fringes and 146-degree phase difference

On the c-u direction we get 316.7238 phase difference

This means 316 fringes and 14-degree phase difference

Even by the naked eye, if we draw a line on the screen that rotates along with the double slit experiment setup, we should be able to see there is one fringe added in one direction and when we rotate the setup, 180 degrees the same fringe moves out of the line.

If isotropy of light is true, then we should not be able to see the fringe movement between different directions.

As this setup is in the xy plane, the fringe movement was observed between north and south directions. As the earth moves along with the sun in the direction of north, we see c+u direction, and on the opposite direction, south, we observe c-u direction. By introducing a lens that could expand the gaps between the fringes, we could observe the movement of the fringes better.

If we construct another setup which is in xz plane, and combine the results, we could effectively calculate velocity and direction of our reference frame. Constructing a setup where exact phase difference can be measured would lead to a very accurate measurements of velocity and direction of the local reference frame with respect to a preferred reference frame where the velocity of light is constant in all directions.

The above setup can be constructed as semi globe that can house a double slit setup where the inner perimeter is studded with nano scale photo diodes which can measure the phase differences. Two such semi globes could effectively be connected to provide the direction and velocity of the local reference frame.

V. IMPLICATIONS OF NON-ISOTROPY OF LIGHT

The special theory of relativity is associated with two thought experiments. One is the light coming from a place that is received by both the stationary and moving frame of references. And the presumption is that both observers perceive the velocity of light is constant (2).

Figure 3. The same event (solid dot) that emits light is perceived by the frame S' as well as S. This thought experiment presumes that both the frames perceive the velocity of light is constant and same which is c.

This thought experiment produces the following equation for the time dilation.

$$\Delta t' = \frac{\Delta t - \frac{u}{c^2} \Delta x}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{u^2}{c^2}}}$$

The other one is the moving light clock. In this case the light travels between two plates, and each tick is counted as a measure of the time.

Figure 4: The thought experiment in which the light travels from bottom to top between two plates while both the plates are traveling at the velocity of u .

This thought experiment produces the following time dilation equation.

$$\Delta t' = \frac{\Delta t}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{u^2}{c^2}}}$$

- Eq 5.2

Both produce the same length contraction equation.

But the second thought experiment does not presume that the velocity of light is constant for all the observers. While the first one assumes the one-way velocity of light as constant, there is no proof for that. What we could verify was always the two-way velocity of light which was found to be constant. This is what is proved in the Michelson Morley experiment as well.

The experimental setup as depicted in this paper details how the velocity of the reference frame be measured against the velocity of light, the presumption of the first thought experiment does not seem consistent with nature.

Thus, the time dilation equation will be

$$\Delta t' = \frac{\Delta t}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{u^2}{c^2}}}$$

- Eq 5.3

As the velocity of the local reference frame is measurable, the time dilation of any reference frame can be calculated as below.

$$t_p = \Delta t' + t_L$$

- Eq 5.4

where

t_p is the time in the preferred frame (or universal reference frame)

$\Delta t'$ is the calculated time dilation

t_L is the time in the local frame

Hence the universal time will be the time when the velocity of the local reference frame is zero in all directions. This is the reference frame when the velocity of light is constant in all directions.

In the equation 5.1. the light cone of causality is when u is always less than the value of c . Since this is no longer the case, the light cone of causality does not exist. And it is potentially possible for a local frame to travel faster than the speed of light. But as the equation 5.2 states, that in any local frame the velocity of local frame cannot exceed the velocity of light

$$\Delta t' = \frac{\Delta t}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{u^2}{c^2}}}$$

- Eq 5.5

If at any time the $\Delta t'$ is positive, the Δt is also positive. Hence there is no such time as there will be a break from the causality. If at any time, the u becomes greater than c , then the $\Delta t'$ becomes imaginary number, hence cannot happen.

If the velocity of the local frame equals or exceeds the velocity of light, then the light from plate A cannot touch the plate B, hence the time stands still for the local frame. In other words, physically impossible for any local frame to be in state of velocity more than the velocity of light, in which all the clocks and all the machines cease to function. Force transfer happens because of the interaction of force carriers which are photons. As the velocity of the reference frame increases, incrementally more energy needs to be spent. This makes progressively tougher to increase the speed of the reference frame closer and closer to the velocity of light.

Many attempts have been made to bring back simultaneity to the special relativity. Mansouri, R., Sexl, R.U. A test theory of special relativity: I. Simultaneity and clock synchronization. (3) have proposed, but within the Einstein synchronization procedures. As seen here, as the local time dilation is measurable, the simultaneity is restored. Everyone can potentially measure their own time dilation and add that component to the local time to get the universal time.

Isotropy of velocity of light is the reference frame in which the time flows constantly. Every other reference frame will be time dilated. Thus, in the twin's paradox, the twin who goes in a faster reference frame is younger than the twin in which the velocity of the reference frame is slower. The person in the velocity of the reference frame in which the velocity of the reference frame is zero or the velocity of light is constant in all directions will be the oldest.

This brings us the other question of superluminal reference frames.

But suppose a bubble in space is created with meta materials in such a way that the velocity of the light is same in all directions. Inside this reference frame the instruments and the human life would go on as if it is normal irrespective the speed of this bubble.

This is similar to the inside of a supersonic plane. As the inside of a supersonic plane is sealed to the air outside, the sound can travel normally and the people can hear each other. But outside the plane, the sound travels slower than the plane,

and the people inside the plane can't hear the sound plane itself is making.

If it is possible to create such a bubble where the space outside cannot interact with the space inside and the velocity of light is constant in all directions, then that bubble can travel super luminously due to, say, Alcubierre metric (4).

The person inside such a space plane would still be in the same universal time and the simultaneity is established even though the reference frame is traveling in super luminous speeds.

Thus, the time dilation is dependent on the measurable velocity of the reference frame rather than the actual velocity of the reference frame.

VI. CONCLUSION

Practical experimental setup can be built to measure the velocity of the reference frame with respect to the velocity of the light, which can provide the local time dilation with respect to the universal reference time. More accurate laboratory experiments need to be conducted to measure the phase differences and the velocity of local reference frame.

VII. APPENDIX

1. Sample images with the above setup.

On 10-15-2024 10 PM, Edison, NJ, When the setup points to the south, Left side is on the side of the center of double slit, Right side is the screen. The angle is roughly 7 degrees from the center of the double slit.

$$d = .7 \text{ mm}$$

$$\lambda = 520\text{nm (green laser)}$$

for an assumed velocity of the reference frame
 $= 200000 \text{ m/s}$

Distance to the screen 1.2 m

Expected phase difference is
 233.6013202 on c+v direction and
 233.9132123 on c-v direction

When the setup points to the North, Left side is on the side of the center of double slit, Right side is the screen.

2. Sample images with the above setup.

On 10-16-2024 10 PM, Edison, NJ, When the setup points to the south, Left side is on the side of the center of double slit, Right side is the screen.

The angle is roughly 7 degrees from the center of the double slit.

$$d = .7 \text{ mm}$$

$$\lambda = 520\text{nm (green laser)}$$

for an assumed velocity of the reference frame
 $= 200000 \text{ m/s}$

Distance to the screen 1.2 m

Expected phase difference is
 233.6013202 on c+v direction and
 233.9132123 on c-v direction

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When the setup points to the North, Left side is on the side of the center of double slit, Right side is the screen.

